

RELIGIOSITY AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN OGUN STATE

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Abstract

The study examined the relationship among religiosity, locus of control and academic achievement of students in Colleges of Education in Ogun State. The subjects comprised 125 students randomly selected from two colleges of education in Ogun State. A Religiosity Scale fashioned in line with Strayhorn Religiosity Scale (1990) was used to assess the religiosity level of the students; an adapted version of Rotter's Locus of Control Scale (1966) was utilized to measure students' locus of control score and an Academic Achievement Scale was used to measure students' academic achievement. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistic. The result showed that religiosity and locus of control were in moderate positive correlation with achievement in Measurement and Evaluation. In addition, a significant positive correlation was also established between religiosity and students' locus of control. The study recommended among others that advisors should go beyond the academic field and help students to improve and understand how their perception of self and their environment may shape their academic performance.

Keywords: religiosity; locus of control; religiosity scale; locus of control scale; academic achievement scale.

Introduction

Over the years, there has been a considerable amount of debate on the effects of religion on education. The larger portion of this debate has focused on the effects of private religious schools on the academic achievement of children (Chubb & Moe, 1990; Coleman, Hoffer, & Kilgore, 1982; Bryk, Lee, & Holland, 1993). That is, most

of this debate has focused on the school level of investigation rather than the student level. One can argue that the individual religious beliefs of students are just as important as, and perhaps more important than, the beliefs of the educational institution attended. To the extent that this is true, it may be that the historic academic advantage that students of religious schools have had over students from public schools may have as much to do with the individual levels of religious commitment of the students than whether they attend a public or religious school. As some social scientists have pointed out, there have been only a small number of studies that address this issue directly (Brody, Stoneman, & Flor, 1996; Oh, 1984; Zern, 1987).

A number of social scientists believe the influence of religion, whether through personal devotion or schooling, may play a special role in urban settings (Jeynes, 1999, 2001; Sander, 1996). Educational psychologists and sociologists have been quick to point out that there are unique challenges that adolescents face in urban settings, particularly in the inner city (Jeynes, 2000; Jeynes & Littell, 2000; Sander, 1996). Several researchers have presented analyses and hypotheses that suggest that religion, whether expressed in religious schools or in religiosity, apparently helps children overcome many of these challenges so that they excel both academically and socially (Bryk, Lee & Holland, 1993; Coleman et al., 1982; Jeynes, 1999). For example, some social scientists argue that religious schools do a better job of helping disadvantaged students (Coleman, 1988; Coleman et al., 1982; Gaziel, 1997; Marsch, 1991; Morris, 1994). Lee (1986), for example, found that religious schools tend to reduce the achievement gap that frequently exists between Whites and African Americans. Other research indicates that religious commitment also reduces that gap (Jeynes, 2003).

For quite sometime, some researchers have been addressing the issue of the effects of individual religious commitment on academic achievement. Research has examined the relationship between the formal religious commitments of the parents and the academic achievement of children (Brody et al., 1996). Zern (1989) examined the effects of student religious commitment on college academic achievement. He found that religious commitment was related to a student's chances of living up to his or her ability level (as measured by the Scholastic Aptitude Test, SAT and Graduate Record Examination, GRE), although it was found that students who were more religious did not show any tendency to perform better academically than their less religious counterparts. Koubek (1984) found that among Christian high school

students, there was a positive correlation between the degree of religious commitment and academic achievement. Similarly, a study by Oh (1999) found that high school students who had a high level of religiosity were more likely to have a higher GPA than non-religious students. Nevertheless, the number of studies attempting to understand the relationship between individual religious commitment and academic achievement is still quite small. Instead, researchers have tended to prefer to study the educational achievements of religious schools versus non-religious schools.

The fact that a high level of religious commitment has other positive effects may lead one to suspect that a high level of religious commitment by students would benefit them academically. For example, research has shown that religious commitment can help people deal with social situations and stress (Pargament, 1990; Seligman, 1991; Thomas & Carver, 1990), deal with traumatic loss such as the loss of a loved one (Balk, 1983; Palmer & Noble, 1986), have family stability (Filsinger & Wilson, 1984; Shrum, 1980), and have good physical health (McIntosh & Spilka, 1990).

On the basis of research that has been done on the effects of religious faith on various individuals, there are some reasons to think that the religious faith of students may influence their academic achievement in a positive way. The first of these reasons, and probably the most acknowledged, deals with a religious work ethic. Although, this work ethic is commonly referred to as the "Protestant work ethic," recent research indicates that this work ethic may extend beyond the Protestant sphere to other religious groups as well. Mentzer (1988), for example, has found that Catholics in America possess a strong work ethic. Research in the social sciences has consistently indicated the existence of a religious work ethic (Furnham, 1987; Gerhards, 1996; Giorgi & Marsh, 1990; Mudrack, 1992). Busto (1996) and Ter Voert (1993) found that this religious work ethic transcends differences in race and nationality. Giorgi and Marsh (1990) produced evidence suggesting that a religious work ethic can become strong enough to pervade an entire culture. A religious work ethic in the life of a student may also have a particular effect, given that some studies suggest that an ethic of "leisure" is becoming more prominent in Western society (Reeves & Petty, 1982). Although there are some studies such as that undertaken by Chusmir and Koberg (1988) that suggest the relationship between religious commitment and a work ethic is overstated, most studies have found a consistent

relationship between the two.

A second reason to believe there might be a relationship between religious commitment and academic achievement emerges from the tendency for religious people to abstain from behaviors that are often regarded as undisciplined and harmful to academic achievement. A number of studies indicate that religiously committed teens are less likely to become involved in drug and alcohol abuse (Bahr, Hawks, & Wang, 1993; Brownfield & Sorenson, 1991; Nylander, Tung, & Xu, 1996). Other studies indicate that religiously committed teens are less likely to engage in sexual behaviour or become pregnant while they are still teenagers (Beck, Cole, & Hammond, 1991; Holman & Harding, 1996; Miller & Olson, 1988).

A third reason stems from the finding of some studies that suggest that religious people are more likely to have an internal locus of control (Jackson & Coursey, 1988; Shrauger & Silverman, 1971). Educational researchers have found a rather consistent relationship between possessing an internal locus of control and performing well in school (Garner & Cole, 1986; Johnson, 1992).

Locus of control refers to an individual's generalized expectations concerning where control over subsequent events resides. In other words, who or what is responsible for what happens. Locus of control is an individual's belief system regarding the causes of his or her experiences and the factors to which that person attributes success or failure. Locus of control can be divided into two sources of control: internal and external. People with an internal locus of control believe that they control their own destiny. They also believe that their own experiences are controlled by their own skill or efforts. On the other hand, people who tend to have an external locus of control tend to attribute their experiences to fate, chance, or luck.

The literature available on locus of control and academic achievement was reviewed by Findley and Cooper (1983), cited in Grants (2002). They compiled 98 studies (consisting of 275 testable hypotheses) where a locus of control and academic achievement measure was compared. A statistically significant positive correlation was found for 193 out of the 275 hypotheses. In other words, 70% of these hypotheses found internals to have significantly higher academic achievement than externals. Bar-Tal and Bar-Zohar in Bar-On (2002) reviewed 36 studies that examined the relationship between locus of control and academic achievement among children, adolescents and adults. They also found a positive correlation between the two variables, regardless of population being examined. Within the domain of education,

internal locus of control has been found to be a positive predictor of academic achievement (Keith, Pottebaum & Eberhardt, 1986) and external locus of control to be a negative predictor of academic achievement (Eachus & Cassidy, 1997).

A study by Murk and Addleman (1992) found that students who had a high level of moral reasoning were also more likely to have an internal locus of control. Many religious organizations feel that it is their duty to teach moral values, so one can assume that religious students are also likely to score high on a moral reasoning scale. Strayhorn (1966) has found that people, who have a high need for achievement, also have a belief in their own ability or skill to determine the outcome of their efforts. Someone with an internal locus of control would most likely believe in working to be a good person so that he can reach a higher spiritual state. This individual may also believe in studying and working hard in order to get good grades.

Statement of the Problem

Academic achievement is something that every parent wishes for their child. However, determining exactly what it is that causes students to excel is not an easy task. Evidence from literature, personal observation and experience indicate that individuals who have a high level of religiosity are less likely to engage in risky behaviour than their counterpart with low level of religiosity and consequently translate to differences in their academic achievement. Again, it could be reasoned that the locus of control of religious individuals would be more internal than the non-religious individuals owing to the moral values usually taught by religious organizations to their members and at such influence their academic achievement positively. The study, therefore, seeks to establish the relationship among the three variables: religiosity, locus of control and academic achievement of students in colleges of education in Ogun State.

Hypotheses

- Three hypotheses were formulated to guide the conduct of the study. They are
1. There will be no significant relationship between religiosity and academic achievement of students.
 2. There will be no significant relationship between locus of control and academic achievement of students.
 3. There will be no significant relationship between religiosity and locus of control of students.

Method

The study adopted the descriptive survey research type. The subjects comprised 125 students, made up of 79 female and 46 male, randomly selected from two colleges of education in Ogun State (1 Federal and 1 State). The mean age of subjects was 21.6 years. Twenty-eight point two percent of subjects indicated they were in their first year, 34.3% were in their second year and 37.5% indicated they had been in college for three years or more.

The following instruments were used to obtain data for the study. A Religiosity Scale fashioned in line with Strayhorn Religiosity Scale (1990). The scale enjoyed a concurrent validity coefficient of 0.78 ($n = 40$) with the Strayhorn scale and a split-half reliability coefficient of 0.81. A Locus of Control Scale adapted from Rotter's Locus of Control Scale (1966). The scale had a concurrent validity coefficient of 0.71 ($n = 40$) with the Rotter's scale and a split-half reliability coefficient of 0.76. The third instrument was an Academic Achievement Scale, which contained items regarding a student's perceived academic achievement in the college. The experimenter personally administered the three instruments with the help of some lecturers in the institutions and the students' responses were carefully collated for subsequent analysis. Data obtained were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistic with the significant level set at 0.05.

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Results

Table 1 shows descriptive statistics of the variables.

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation for the variables

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Religiosity Scale	33.2960	8.52702	125
Locus of Control Scale	12.3680	2.92524	125
Academic Achievement Scale	34.8400	8.91031	125

Table 2: Correlation matrix of Religiosity, Locus of control and Academic achievement.

		Religiosity Scale	Locus of Control Scale	Academic Achievement Scale
Religiosity Scale	Pearson Correlation	1	.291(**)	.502(**)
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	.000
	N	125	125	125
Locus of Control Scale	Pearson Correlation	.291(**)	1	.494(**)
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001		.000
	N	125	125	125
Academic Achievement Scale	Pearson Correlation	.502(**)	.494(**)	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	125	125	125

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Hypothesis 1

The first null hypothesis stated that there will be no significant relationship between religiosity and academic achievement of students. Contrary to this hypothesis, the correlation matrix presented in table 2 indicated a positively significant relationship between religiosity and students' academic performance ($r = .502, p < 0.05$). Hence the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis 2

The second null hypothesis stated that there will be no significant relationship between locus of control and academic achievement of students. This hypothesis was rejected on the basis of the results in table 2 which revealed a significant positive relationship between the two variables ($r = .494, p < 0.05$).

Hypothesis 3

The third null hypothesis stated that there will be no significant relationship between religiosity and students' locus of control. Table 2 also showed a significant positive relationship, even though low, between religiosity and students' locus of control ($r = .291, p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was again rejected.

Discussion

The findings in hypothesis 1 revealed that there is a significant relationship between religiosity and academic achievement of students. This finding is in consonance with the result of the study conducted by Zern (1989) who examined the effects of student religious commitment on college academic achievement. He found that religious commitment was related to a student's chances of living up to his or her ability level (as measured by the SAT and GRE). Oh (1999) also found that high school students who had a high level of religiosity were more likely to have a higher GPA than non-religious students.

A likely reason for this finding emerges from the tendency for religious people to abstain from behaviours that are often regarded as undisciplined and harmful to academic achievement such as getting involved in drugs and alcohol abuse or engaging in sexual behaviour or becoming pregnant. Their non-religious counterparts who often engage in unwholesome behaviours may not have the time and concentration required for high academic achievement in their studies.

In hypothesis 2, it was found that there is a significant relationship between students' locus of control and academic achievement. The results is in conformity with the findings of studies reviewed by Findley and Cooper (1983), cited in Grants (2002) which reveal a statistically significant positive correlation between locus of control and academic achievement. In other words, the review showed that students with internal locus of control have significantly higher academic achievement than external. Similarly, Bar-Tal and Bar-Zohar cited in Bar-On (2002) also found, in their

own review, a positive correlation between the two variables, regardless of population being examined.

A plausible reason for this finding is that it seems logical that individuals with an internal locus of control achieve more academically than individuals with an external locus of control. This is because, an internal student, who studies hard and performed well on a test, will attribute the success to his own actions. This student will then continue to study hard, as an expectation to succeed in the future is obvious. Moreover, the individual feels a positive emotional response of pride for the successes, which strengthens his expectation and motivation. On the other hand, an external student may study and do well on a test, but may believe the success is due to an easy test, or luck or a variety of other factors. This student does not attribute success to his own actions, and so may not consistently study.

The third hypothesis found that there is a significant relationship between religiosity and students' locus of control. The finding is in agreement with that of Jackson and Coursey (1988) and the one found by Shrauger and Silverman (1971). Their results showed that religious people are more likely to have an internal locus of control. Also, Murk and Addleman (1992), in a study, found that students who had a high level of moral reasoning were also more likely to have an internal locus of control.

A likely reason for this result is that a religious student owing to the imbibed moral standard gained from the teachings of religious organizations may have a firm belief in the fact that the more he studies the better grades he gets. In other words, he is in control of his successes or failure.

Conclusion

Religiosity and students' locus of control, among others, are two non-cognitive variables which have direct influence on performance in school subjects. Both religiosity and locus of control correlate positively with academic achievement of students. Even though the relationship is low, religiosity also has a positive correlation with students' locus of control. Conflicting results on the relationship between religiosity and locus of control from some studies may be due to variation in sample of students used, poor research methodology, scale used etc. Finally, it is concluded that individual student's religious commitment affect academic performance.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made to bring about increased academic performance of students in Measurement and Evaluation in Colleges of Education.

Since religious commitment of individual students have been found to improve academic performance and moral standing, efforts should therefore be made by school authorities, parents, government and other stakeholders in the education industry to encourage the teaching of religious subjects in schools. In addition, places of worship should be provided in our institutions of learning to cater for the spiritual and moral needs of students. This will go a long way in stemming the incidence of cult activities and other social vices rampant in our schools.

Advisors should go beyond the academic field and help students to improve and understand how their perceptions of self and their environment may change their academic performance. Therefore, advising students could expand to include mentoring and modeling them. Academic and personal mentoring of students serve as a conduit to a healthy attitude towards academic work, study habits, orientation to others and their college. College orientation sessions should include presentations and classes on the variables that affect grade-point averages. At the macro level, governance and administrators in Colleges of Education should develop policies regarding coaching mentoring and counseling of students.

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The descriptions above negate the optimism of most observers of Nigeria state who see the country as a dynamic economy. This optimism is premised on the abundant natural and material resources which the country is endued with by nature.

It is of course true that the economic fortunes of a country are determined by a variety of factors. In the case of Nigeria, the collapse of the international oil market is a very important variable in the nature, state and character of any nation. Leadership and the form of leadership that they provide shape the way in which state policies are made and the impact on the general life of the people. State and course of actions at both the domestic and international levels. Ironically, the political class or the decision makers of a state who determine the purpose and course of actions at both the domestic and international levels. This conditions of Nigeria and Nigerians over the years have remained pathetic. The leadership has been described as not focused, sincere, honest and corrupt. All these vices, it is said, lead to bad government. The resultant effect is the general level of poverty, insecurity, unemployment and deprivation. The paper finally submits that to redress the situation, there is the urgent need to reform the country through honest, transparent, dedicated, committed and distributed, national leader who could transform the country to a truly federal state with every citizen feeling a genuine sense of belonging. Every part of the country should be fully facilitated so that it is the political class or the leadership of a state, therefore the idiosyncrasies of leaders go a long way to